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FEATURES AND TRENDS OF EDUCATIONAL CHANGES' APPROACHES IN WORLD-CLASS ENGINEERING UNIVERSITIES: BASED ON RESEARCH OF THREE UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

The spread of COVID-19 and other 21st century's grand challenges of the have propelled the global process of engineering education transformation. Therefore, how to choose an appropriate path of education change in the coming years, and quicken the pace for the provision of high-quality and large-scale education engineering is of great significance for lots of universities and colleges, since they must grasp the historical window period for the adjustment of global engineering education leadership landscape. From the perspective of institutional entrepreneurship, this paper has viewed the engineering education changes in universities as a process in which universities acquire resources to create new institutions or change existing ones in different field conditions and under different circumstances. This paper is based on the theoretical framework of institutional entrepreneurship, introduces legitimacy as a theoretical tool, and selects three world-class engineering universities, that is MIT (USA), Tsinghua University (China), and TU Delft (Netherlands) under different educational systems for case studies and inductive logic analysis of their significant education changes in the past ten years. This paper has drawn the features and trends of these universities in developing education change programs or initiatives vis integrated comparison to provide some useful insights to new participants endeavoring to change in engineering education. It may also make some knowledge contribution to the engineering education community.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Engineering education has always reflected the social and economic needs and changes. However, from a historical point of view, higher engineering education has gradually lost students' preference for engineering majors in the enrollment market, and the graduate employment market is also facing a situation where enterprises' recognition of cultivating talents is reduced. A significant reason is that engineering education in universities has maintained the traditional education models for most students. Therefore, the engineering education community has always regarded educational reform as one of the crucial issues of its research list. There is such a long road for engineering education change yet. Some researches suggest that this is due to the powerful anti-change forces that are associated.^[1] Based on the network location theory, several universities at the center of engineering education systems come up with facts that they have presented the top engineering education quality nationwide, so they do not have to change. In contrast, universities on the edge of the network are always limited by material and technical resources but may have the will to change. This situation may lead to collective silence among engineering universities to preserve the status quo.

1.2 Purpose

Regarding the question of how universities should carry out engineering education changes, two very different views emerged in the existing research. It may be due to the widespread resistance to change in colleges and universities. Some studies believe that although each university's engineering education change is not suitable for a one-size-fits-all solution, a university adopts an incremental change plan based on its partial proved successful experiences and suits its reality is still the mainstream path of change in engineering education.^[1] However, other scholars have found successful transformative initiatives usually avoid the incremental approach, but adopt radical and systematic approach instead, based on the survey results of engineering education programs in multiple countries.^[2]

The American Journal of Engineering Education published a special issue of "The Complexities of Transforming Engineering Higher Education" in 2014. It pointed out that since the engineering education community has made a lot of contributions to the reform process, models of specific courses and curriculum, engineering educators and researchers should strengthen the knowledge base focused on the systematic educational change programs and initiatives of universities by more participation.^[3] This study is based on the multi-situational institutional change process framework of institutional entrepreneurship theory. It summarizes the features and trends of the world-class engineering universities in carrying out significant educational change programs or initiatives by multi-case and inductive logic analysis^[4]. It attempts to contribute to presents some worthwhile observations of systematic education change in engineering education and provide some useful insights into new global participants with on-

going efforts in engineering education. In this study, a university's engineering education (significant) change refers to the programs or initiatives carried out using rigorous methods and convincing evidence based on extensive investigations.^[5]

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research approach

Seely B.(1999) shared that "perhaps the most constant feature of American engineering education has been the demand for change" after reviewing American engineering education history. It applies to engineering education not only in the US but also in Asia, Europe, and the world. To enhance sufficient quality of the data in this study, we adopted the following criteria for selecting the case study objects: firstly, It provides the world-class education quality recognized by the engineering education community; secondly, it has developed at least one significant education change in the past ten years, and the results of the change have significantly improved or consolidated its reputation and status in engineering education; thirdly, it represents the geographical location, national institution system and background of a specific type of engineering universities; finally, it has sufficient records for the historical documents and of major events of its educational changes^[4].

Based on these standards, With the literature work and knowledge of the global engineering education community, we choose the case studies from the top ten universities of both "current leader" and "emerging leaders" identified in MIT's influential report(2018) "The global state of the art in engineering education," which are the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the United States, Tsinghua University in China, and the Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands eventually.

2.2 Research design

2.2.1 Theoretical orientation of institutional entrepreneurship

Institutional entrepreneurship has now become synonymous with institutional change. The concept of institutional entrepreneurship was proposed to find a solution to the "Paradox of Embedded Agency." When DiMaggio(1988) first explained institutional entrepreneurship's phenomenon, he believed that "new institutions arise when organized actors with sufficient resources see in them an opportunity to realize interests that they value highly." ^[6] His statement mentioned a sequence: the actors of the organization firstly have sufficient resources, then find opportunities for institutional entrepreneurship, and it refers more to the centric organizations' institutional entrepreneurship in a mature field. To avoid the discussion of complex elements in the institutional entrepreneurship process, Dorado(2005) comprehensively discussed three general factors commonly define institutional entrepreneurship, field condition, agency, and resource mobilization, and proposed ten different combinations, which clarified the conceptual relationship between the three factors, and formed a framework for research on institutional change under various circumstances. ^[7]

This article aims at the world-class engineering universities that have carried out significant engineering education changes, which are generally in the field of a complete and open engineering education system. For focusing on the research purpose

and consciously breaking out of the “complex dilemma” of engineering education changes’ research in universities, we targeted the field of “opportunity transparency” in Dorado’s work as the initial theoretical framework (Table 1).

Table 1. The initial theoretical framework

Field Condition: Opportunity	Agency	Resource mobilization	Profile
transparent	strategic	leverage	entrepreneurship
		accumulation	partaking
	sensemaking	accumulation	partaking
	routine	accumulation	partaking

2.2.2 Legitimacy mechanisms as the theoretical tool

The evolution of organizations not only stems from the pressure of technology and material resources, but also from the constraints of social and cultural norms, symbols, beliefs, and customs^[8] such as "legitimacy," which is emerged as "a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions" in the 1990s.^[9] Legitimacy is one of the core ideas to explain the convergence of organizational system structure. It comes from people's perception of whether a thing or action meets norms and expectations, and generally has been divided into three types, regulative legitimacy, and normative legitimacy, and cognitive legitimacy.^[10]

From a strategic perspective, legitimacy is an invisible and essential resource that can help an organization obtain other resources. Organization managers or institutional entrepreneurs can actively obtain legitimacy in purposeful approaches, which is reflected in multiple phases of institutional entrepreneurship six phases-process-model in the mature field that is comprehensively sorted out by Greenwood et al. (2002). As center organizations in mature fields, benchmarking universities enjoy vested interests in an engineering education system with sufficient resources in terms of material and technology. Therefore, introducing different legitimacies’ acquisition into the research on transformation models of engineering education may have the opportunity to unify the divergence of views mentioned earlier in 1.2. Thus we expand the initial framework as follows (Table 2).

Table 2. The theoretical framework embodies legitimacy mechanisms

Field Condition: Opportunity	Agency	Resource mobilization			Profile
		regulative legitimacy	normative legitimacy	cognitive legitimacy	
transparent	strategic	leverage			entrepreneurship
		accumulation			partaking
	sensemaking	accumulation			partaking
	routine	accumulation			partaking

2.2.3 Data sources

We collected the data from three sources: (i) information related to engineering education changes from the three universities' website during 2013-2020; (ii) 17 articles of journals or conference proceedings from professional association publications (ASEE, CSEE, and SEFI), which are about the effort of the three universities to transform engineering education; (iii) the related introduction report such as "The global state of the art in engineering education" and policy documents.

2.2.4 Data analysis

The research adopted the case study research method. It had three professional associations' publications as the starting point of analysis and compiled the three universities' major events in the process of engineering education changes.

Secondly, employing "snowballing," we track the detailed descriptions of various initiatives during the three universities' education change processes to form the strategic items adopted by each university in each major event. Then, according to the institution entrepreneurship strategy set, the strategies corresponding to each event are generally coded.

Thirdly, the resource types of legitimacy are identified from the established strategies' general codes with each strategy's influence on the change process, based on the iteration of literature analysis, three universities' official information, and reports.

Fourthly, under the expanded theoretical framework, we identified the features and trends of world-class engineering universities' education changes under different backgrounds.

2.2.5 Limitations

It should be acknowledged that the case-study method will have shortcomings that cannot be generalized due to the small sample size in qualitative research. In order to discover the generalities in the three universities' changes as much as possible, the study improved the existing theoretical framework of institutional entrepreneurship under multi-circumstances and selected the two possible change paths of three world-class engineering universities with different national backgrounds.

It is almost impossible to make the three universities perform engineering education changes entirely during the same period, and it is hard for horizontal contrast. Since the transformative process always includes two phases, the gestation phase, and the implementation phase, the study can assure the main critical period (2016-2020) that spanning the boundary between two phases can be covered.

Table 3. An integrated comparison between the engineering education changes in three universities

	MIT	Tsinghua University	TU Delft												
National context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cope with the 21st century's grand challenges maintain global leadership transforming undergraduate education in engineering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aim to become an engineering education power urgent need to improve the quality and deepen comprehensive reform in higher education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> usefulness-oriented problem-solving nationwide cooperation culture 												
University's context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lead future development respond to major challenges develop MIT community's the ability and passion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> persist in serving the country take national higher education reform pilot tasks strive for self-improvement and excellence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> solve social problems fewer bureaucracies inclusive and egalitarian 												
Significant education programs	New Engineering Education Transformation (NEET, 2016-2020)	Tsinghua University Comprehensive Reform Plan (TUCRP, 2012-2020)	TU Delft Strategic Framework (TUDSF, 2014-2020)												
Change phases	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gestation</th> <th>Implementation</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> formulated NEET approach gathered documented evidence, and survey worked on pilot threads, NEET curricular & freshman programs launched the process of building the NEET community... </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> launched four pilot threads, plan for upgrading them to 3/4th-year program evaluated the program and departments' thread proposal requests NEET seminars, marketing and recruiting students cross-school initiatives, thread community plan... explore threads to 3/4th-year program & planned degree programs </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gestation	Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> formulated NEET approach gathered documented evidence, and survey worked on pilot threads, NEET curricular & freshman programs launched the process of building the NEET community... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> launched four pilot threads, plan for upgrading them to 3/4th-year program evaluated the program and departments' thread proposal requests NEET seminars, marketing and recruiting students cross-school initiatives, thread community plan... explore threads to 3/4th-year program & planned degree programs 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gestation</th> <th>Implementation</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> undertook the task with Ministry of Education's approval gathered stakeholders' suggestions of the preliminary plan... Tsinghua's 24th educational work discussion the state approved the Reform Plan </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> reform of personnel system new education system & programs mechanism... re-constructed programs' plan based on a global investigation four departments' pilots Tsinghua's 25th educational work discussion TUCRP Summary Working Group's working for follow-up advancement </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gestation	Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> undertook the task with Ministry of Education's approval gathered stakeholders' suggestions of the preliminary plan... Tsinghua's 24th educational work discussion the state approved the Reform Plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reform of personnel system new education system & programs mechanism... re-constructed programs' plan based on a global investigation four departments' pilots Tsinghua's 25th educational work discussion TUCRP Summary Working Group's working for follow-up advancement 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Gestation</th> <th>Implementation</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a department's Education Director published an influential report caused broad discussion announced the start of an institution-wide strategic framework process launched several initiatives the establishment of Teaching Academy... </td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> articulated TU Delft's educational vision released TU Delft Strategic Framework work 2018-2024 </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gestation	Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a department's Education Director published an influential report caused broad discussion announced the start of an institution-wide strategic framework process launched several initiatives the establishment of Teaching Academy... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> articulated TU Delft's educational vision released TU Delft Strategic Framework work 2018-2024
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Action strategy (Agency)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the framework, bridging diverse stakeholders, creating standards, building coalition... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> taking what the system gives; bridging diverse stakeholders; direct authority... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> educating, routinizing, embedding; bridging diverse stakeholders... 												
Resource mobilization* change approach	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1</th> <th>1-2</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1-2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>incremental change</p>	1	1-2	1	1-2	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1-2</th> <th>2-3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1-2</td> <td>2-3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>systemic change</p>	1-2	2-3	1-2	2-3	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>2</th> <th>2-3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2-3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>incremental change</p>	2	2-3	2	2-3
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Note: * means the average value of three types of legitimacy resources (regulative/ normative/ cognitive legitimacy) acquired for each major event at a specific stage.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Features of significant engineering education changes in three universities

Under the influence of the educational values and organizational culture, the three universities have adopted a gradual or radical way to blaze its own engineering education change "road" across the campus with its characteristics. (Table 3)

3.1.1 MIT

MIT upholds the values of leading the future development, bearing on the world's grand challenges, and developing in each member of the MIT community the ability and passion. The university academic leaders believe any change requires a change in culture that builds on the university's values.^[10] MIT's institutional entrepreneurs pre-conceived a future-oriented and feasible action framework, adopting a strategic agency to guide the behaviors of the MIT community consciously. For example, all departments of the School of Engineering are required to engage in the development of pilot threads gradually, then it comes to the fulfillment of threads, curriculum, and restructured degree programs. MIT also innovated NEET's multi-disciplinary groups under teachers' and students' co-governance at the very beginning and has made specific plans for building the NEET communities to guide the community members' behavior. From the gestation phase to the implementation phase, the accumulation of legitimacy types shows an increasing trend, ensuring MIT's trigger for large-scale engineering education changes after 2020.

3.1.2 Tsinghua University

Tsinghua University has undertaken one of the reform pilot tasks under the national medium and long-term educational reform and development requirements and the responsibility of benchmarking universities, striving to explore resolutions firstly in the national deepening education reform field and accumulate extensional experience. After the state-approved Tsinghua's TUCRP initiative in 2014, the university has conducted the change from the "up-bottom," following TUCRP. In this process, the following senior use of political skills. For example, the university first "wielded the sword" at its own teachers' personnel system, which is widely considered to cause high resistance to change, and abandon the local "incremental reform" that can temporarily avoid contradictions, but directly transformed the management system for teachers overall. By the leveraging approach of agency, its senior managers have acquired a large number of legitimacy resources, especially with the dominant role of regulative legitimacy.

3.1.3 TU Delft

TU Delft has a profound consensus-building culture and the unique "Delft spirit."^[11] The report "Engineering Education in a Rapidly Changing World" written by a department's Director of Education sparked horizon-scanning debates both within and spanning the boundary of TU Delft. Then TU Delft is embodied in that after an influential report, "Engineering Education in a Rapidly Changing World" written by a department's Director of Education sparked horizon-scanning debates both within and spanning the boundary of TU Delft. After that, the university has established 4TU, launched seminars, built up its "Free Spirit Think Tank" and the Teaching Academy, formed its first

university-wide educational vision statement, and then released the Strategic Framework. TU Delft did not follow the "Means-End Chain," but went the way that all the active participants firstly gave meanings to the current situation based on their understandings, formed the identical concepts, and then constructed, refined, formed a framework, and launched a clear action strategy. The action strategy approach makes the university's agency at each phase focused on accumulating a variety of legitimacy types and ultimately promoting a large-scale change.

3.2 Trends of educational changes' approaches in world-class engineering universities

3.2.1 Both incremental and systemic changes will become effective choices for the path of education change

The three universities are gradually and cautiously advancing the process of change, moving in the direction of widespread sustainable change. Indeed, some inquiry results show that good practices of a specific curriculum or course can provide a model for the same department, but they are not enough to drive the university's overall engineering education change. However, through interdisciplinary projects work and a project-based curriculum organization mode, incremental changes have made it possible to provide the teaching approaches and methods for the faculty with a broader professional field. For example, MIT did not require all departments of the School of Engineering to participate in the initial pilot thread task in the process of change. The cross-professional and interdisciplinary characteristics of the thread task enable all relevant departments to engage in a relatively short time. At the same time, there is evidence that systemic change is also a valid path. Tsinghua University completed the restructuring of the overall education programs early. It also adopted the four departments of the School of Mechanical Engineering as enrollment and education pilots of the new programs and then completed the new programs across the campus.

3.2.1 Purposeful acquisition of legitimacy resources has the potential to become a basis for examining whether the education change will maintain the sustainability and effectiveness

From the perspective of engineering education changes' launching approaches, both MIT and TU Delft are incremental, while Tsinghua University is radical and systemic. No matter which kind of change, the legitimacy resources acquired in the implementation phase are more than those in the gestation phase. Every major event will be accompanied by the acquisition of at least one type of legitimacy resource during the engineering education change process. Legitimacy can bring consistency and credibility to universities' engineering education changes, and the more legitimacy types acquire, the more they will promote the community members' consistency of in their actions, and the trust and cultural identity' formation in the cognition. ^[12]

4 SUMMARY

This study has performed a multi-case and inductive logic analysis of significant educational changes developed by world-class engineering universities under the theoretical framework of institutional entrepreneurship. It also introduced legitimacy as a

theoretical tool to discuss agency and resource mobilization in each university's educational change process. This research approach has realized the horizontal comparison of engineering education changes carried out by three different universities, which are in the engineering education systems of the US., China, and a European country. To some extent, It may solve the problems of complexity and ambiguity when studying the common analysis of engineering education changes in transnational universities. It also provides some valuable observations for the universities with great interests to develop a radical systematic educational change in engineering education and some insights for more new participants who endeavor to upgrade the leadership in the engineering education sector.

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CONCEPT PAPERS

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